

NEP-2020: Rejuvenating Quality of Indian Education System

Kuljeet Singh (MA Statistics, M, Ed, MPhil Edu, NET, SET), Research Scholar
Department of Education, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab India

Abstract:- Education plays a pivotal role in developing an equitable, just and open society. Providing quality education to realize the India of our dreams; an India which is socially progressive, economically self-sufficient and globally sustainable, has been a constant endeavor of the policy-makers since Independence. In order to achieve this goal, it is important for a nation to identify and channelize the utmost potential of its citizens. So, considering in the significance of the role of education in the nation-building process, the National Education Policy-2020 brings about some ground-breaking and revolutionary transformations in the existing educational ecosystem of our country.. This paper highlights the innovations and adoptions in NEP 2020 as per the existing policies and the spirit of the Constitution of India regarding quality education. The key points of NEP on quality education at all stages, dimensions, aspects in Indian educational system has been discussed in the present paper such as quality learners, teachers, content, processes outcomes etc, Transforming Curricular and Pedagogical Structure, Vocational Training, Reduction of Importance of Board Examination, Holistic Assessment, Teacher Education shall form the basis of this paper. In addition to this, the present paper focussed on one of the four pillars of Access, Equity, Quality and Accountability mentioned in NEP-2020.

Keywords:- National Education Policy-2020, Quality Education, Holistic Assessment, 5+3+3+4 structure, NIPUN Bharat, SAFAL, Multiple Entry-Exit, Teacher Education, NISHTHA, National Research Foundation, Teacher Eligibility Tests,

I. INTRODUCTION

The prosperity of any nation can be gauged by the skills possessed by her citizens. Education is the mirror of any civilisation. Education aims at developing its human resources to the fullest by providing necessary life skills and soft skills and so on. The 21st century learning skills like critical thinking, creativity collaboration, life skills of flexibility, sociability, productivity leadership, growth mindset are to be addressed by the NEP-2020. India has identified certain grey areas in our education system in terms of increasing retention rate of school/college drop-outs, universalization of education, curriculum and pedagogical restructuring, equity and inclusion, governance reforms and so on. Reforms in education through various initiatives by government of in the form of Operation Blackboard, POA 1992, SSA, Mid day meal scheme, SSA, RMSA, National Knowledge Commission, RTE Act 2009 etc. are still illusions. This illusiveness over the years gave an impetus to adopt an

exhaustive, extensive and far reaching, all education system from foundational stage to higher studies, from vocational to adult education in the shape of NEP-2020. The Policy aims at overcoming all the existing bottlenecks from operation and regulation to federal restructuring of education. The policy will pave way towards making India a self-reliant and global knowledge superpower and it will be only done by making education system for school and colleges more flexible, holistic and multi-disciplinary which will bring out their unique capabilities. Our nation has been facing various challenges in ensuring quality education to her citizens. Poor infrastructure, poor pedagogical practices, untrained teachers, theoretical approaches in delivering information to the students, improper assessment and evaluation of child's learning are the grey areas to be addressed by the newly launched educational policy. The policy also talked about creating a research culture among Indian higher education institutions through National Research Foundation which aims at funding, coordinating, promoting research among sciences, technology, social sciences, arts and humanities to overhaul research ecosystem in the country.

➤ Objectives:

1. To discuss the various changes made on quality education in NEP 2020 and its implementation.
2. To outline the various initiatives taken at all stages, dimensions, aspects of quality education in the policy.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a descriptive study. Various secondary sources including NEP-2022 document, journals, e-contents, blogs, magazines, other publications were consulted during the study. The investigator analysed and reviewed various sources to justify the very nature of the paper.

III. NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY-2020

The New Education Policy 2020 is the outcome of the committee formed by erstwhile Ministry of Human Resources Development under the able leadership and guidance of Dr. K. Kasturirangan former chairman of ISRO and completed the process after a marathon discussions, deliberations and suggestions with the various stakeholders in the country on May 31, 2019. The government of India approved NEP-2020 on 29TH July 2020 with various changes in the existing educational system with the intention of fostering quality component in educational system from foundational to higher educational stages of learning. After a long gap of 34 years since NPE-1986, our country seeks to transform the educational system to such an extent to prepare good thoughtful, well rounded individuals with higher order,

creative thinking, ethics, team spirit etc. The changes brought in our educational system will definitely pave the way towards making India a global knowledge superpower. The NEP-2020 seeks to address the challenges of Quality, Affordability etc. Further, NEP 2020 aims at reforming teaching-learning, examinations, assessment and evaluation, strengthening teacher training, reforming the existing exam system, early childhood care and restructuring the regulatory framework of education, quality of research. NEP 2020 proposed 5+3+3+4 system of school education spanning ages 3-18 to modify 10+2 system of school education, teacher education, technology, funding etc.,

A. *Quality Education*

Since the launch of 17 Sustainable Development Goals on 01 January, 2016 by UN, goal Goal-4 and the various initiatives by Government of India quality education has been the top priority of all the successive governments. The governments over the years, are putting every effort to strengthen the basic education keeping in view the educational needs of the disadvantaged group so that the India can become global knowledge. When we deal with the quality education we mean a standard education must be given to all, the content or syllabus must be same for all, improve with the passage of time.

Quality education encompasses all aspects of education viz., learner, teacher, learning environment, curricula, pedagogy, assessment, student support system. All systematic reforms of standardising the education system with the aim of reforming the existing weaknesses to develop new capacities under quality education. Quality is more a systematic trait rather than only a feature of instruction or attainment. As an overarching attribute, quality expresses the system's capacity to reform itself for enhancing its ability to address its own weakness and to develop new capabilities. It is not merely a measure of efficiency but also has value dimension.

B. *VVOB'S Definition of Quality education*

“ A good quality education is one that provides all learners with capabilities they require to become economically productive, develop sustainable livelihoods, contribute to peaceful and democratic societies and enhance individual well-being. The learning outcomes that are required vary according to context but at the end of basic education cycle must include threshold levels of literacy and numeracy, basic scientific knowledge skills including awareness and prevention of diseases. Capacity development to improve the quality of teachers and other education stakeholders is crucial throughout this process “.

Quality of education depend upon characteristic of **learners** (healthy, motivated students) , **processes** (competent teachers using active methodologies) , content (relevant curricula) and **system** (good governance and educationists)

UN Secretary General Ban Ki-moon set the SDG process in motion in 2012 by declaring that every child must be in school, and the quality of those schools must improve

so that students are prepared to be productive citizens, ready to lead the future.

“ Education must fully assume its central role in helping people to forge more just, peaceful and tolerant societies.”

— **Ban Ki-moon, Secretary-General of the United Nations**

The New Education Policy to promote education among people of India is sure to improve the quality of education being rolled out. The policy covers elementary education to colleges in both rural and urban India. The new policy ensures to cover a wide ambit from Early childhood to higher education to professional education to vocational education to teacher education and training to professional education.

It is based on the ground reality of the country's education scenario that puts more emphasis on the creativity and innovation as well as personality development of the students rather than expecting them to score high and memorizing the content without getting a basic grasp of concepts.

The NEP-2020 has made the following efforts to enhance the quality of education in India :

C. *Quality Learners*

The NEP 2020 aims at improving the quality of learners through strengthening and universalising foundational stage learning by attaining Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN) by all students of 3 years accompanied by play way methods thereby fostering creativity, critical thinking abilities, life skills etc. Further, Multidisciplinary education based on liberal education results into the development of multiple capacities in the students .

D. *Change in the Instructional delivery system*

The 10+2 board examination structure has been dropped; the new school structure will be 5+3+3+4, which comes as a big relief; would prove revolutionary. While most of the existing private schools already have the ECCE embedded in their system and will only have to make a slight change in the class structure and objectives of the change.

E. *Quality Content*

The policy emphasize on holistic, integrated, enjoyable learning with shorter curriculum to enhance essential learning and critical thinking ,discovery based, discussion -based and analysis-based learning. Learning through activities and exploration in a child-friendly and child-specific manner.

Moving away from rote learning & memorising to score marks during exams to actual conceptual understanding. Schools will have to adopt the top-down approach.

F. *Quality Assessment*

The National Education Policy 2020 proposed reform in assessment and examination creating holistic progress card, tracking student progress for achieving learning outcomes. It proposed continuous and comprehensive manner using multiple techniques. SAFAL (Structured Assessment for

Analysing Learning) introduced in CBSE Sschools for grades 3, 5 and 8 focussed core concepts, application-based questions and higher order thinking skills. Competency based learning i.e. children advance to the next level of learning outcomes defined for each grade. Board exams will be designed such as to primarily test core capacities, & competencies. The progress card will now be designed to reflect the 360-degree assessment of a student. A multi-dimensional report card will be generated that will reflect the progress & uniqueness of each learner in the cognitive, affective and psycho-motor domains.

IV. TRANSFORMING STUDENTS LEARNING

A. *Emphasizing Basics:*

Mapping of the curriculum across grades and narrowing it to the respective core knowledge only. The focus will be on practical application-based learning. This reduction will create space for teachers to add activities related to experiential learning, creative thinking and critical skills.

B. *Enhancing Foundational and Literacy Skills :*

All schools will have to rework in these areas to bring about a transformation in the teaching strategies so that these foundational skills can be developed, strengthened and achieved by Grade 3. There will need to be more focus at an early age on reading, writing, and learning of basic mathematical concepts. Introducing innovative teaching would be essential to achieve this.

C. *Encouraging Multilingualism :*

Wherever possible, students till Class 5 in schools should be taught in mother tongue or local language. Various studies that show young children best understand things in their mother tongue or home language. So teachers should be encouraged to be bilingual to achieve the best outcomes.

D. *Breaking Subjects Boundaries :*

Multidisciplinary and holistic educational approach between arts and sciences; curricular and extra-curricular activities; vocational & academic streams etc. In order to eliminate harmful hierarchies among or the silo between different areas of learning can be achieved by integrating the subjects and learning areas.

E. *Life Skill Education :*

As mentioned in the NEP one bagless day can be planned for the hands-on learning of the vocational subjects. But the challenge would be how many vocational subjects are chosen, infrastructural changes and teacher availability.

F. *Teacher Education*

The NEP 2020 reckons that the quality education is the measure of teacher education. The researches across the globe have proved the importance of teachers in improving learning process. NEP 2020 stresses on the quality recruitment of teachers on the basis of teacher eligibility tests (CTET, NET, SET) at different levels. It further proposes 4-years Integrated Teacher Education Programme, (ITEP), National, Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST), National Mission for Mentoring (NMM) and atleast 50 hours

of Continous Professional Development (CPD) for every teacher in a year.

The policy aims to make the teacher recruitment process more transparent by halting mass transfers, using computerised systems for automation of the transfer process, and also encourages States to have technology-enabled planning and forecasting exercises to determine vacancies of the subject. National Initiative for School heads' and Teachers' Holistic Advancement (NISHTHA) is a first of its kind teacher training programme under Samagra Shiksha wherein the Government of India, through its academic bodies, NCERT and NIEPA, is taking a lead role in changing the landscape of in-service training.

G. *Higher Education*

NEP 2020 emphasis on quality education through the formulation of National Research Foundation (NRF) as an autonomous body of GOI, to fund, mentor, incentivize and build capacity for quality research across the country in all disciplines, primarily at universities and colleges both public and private. The NRF is mandated with the task of permeating the culture of research and innovation for addressing the societal needs. This policy sees independent, self-governed higher education institutions with capable and ethical leadership as a driver of educational change. It aims at setting up effective and responsive rules and regulations to encourage academic excellence and public hope in higher education.

V. CONCLUSION

Quality of education can be a vital factor in the development of a good citizen. The very goal of quality education can be achieved only if we improve/implement the Sustainable goals initiated by UN and government in true sense. Various stakeholders who are vital components in the decision making process have great role to play. To meet the criteria/level of quality education we the stakeholder must implement the various provisions seriously. Education Policy (NEP) has demonstrated a clear will to move the needle away from the old world of learning. This has been highlighted with the triad of multidisciplinary higher education, multiple options at senior school and multiple chances of success in school-leaving examinations. The focus on foundational learning, the inclusion of the very young into formal learning and the emphasis on holistic learning are goals that are baked into the policy. As institution implement these changes, we will see a shift in the quality education system to one where students receive more conceptual and practical education.

In the backdrops of these reforms, NEP 2020 emphasized the increased focus on overhauling the quality of education by introducing new policy reforms like curriculum reforms, innovative pedagogy, technology enabled teaching, proving pre-vocational skills, research, innovation, encouraging multilingualism, transformation of school education and providing quality education to the last citizen in the last mile. The proposed measures of NEP 2020 if implemented seriously by the stakeholders at the different

levels will definitely make our India Global Super of Knowledge, is the soul of the present paper.

REFERENCES

- [1]. NEP-2020, p6, p20, p42
- [2]. Sarangi Santosh ,”Reinventing Teacher Education “ Yojana Monthly issue, February ,2022, p17.
- [3]. Kumar, Deep,(2020), “A Critical Analysis and a glimpse of New Education Policy-2020 “ International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research ,Volume II, Issue 10, October 2020,ISSN 2229-5518
- [4]. Chopra, Ritika (2 August 2020). “Explained :Reading the New Education Policy 2020 “. The Indian Express.
- [5]. Anand ,Apoorva (February 9,2021),Explained :How will NEP 2020 change the education system in India “. India Today Web Desk, New Delhi .
- [6]. National Education Policy 2020.https://www.mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/nep/NEP_Final_English.pdf
- [7]. <https://www.vvob.org/en/education/our-vision-on-quality-education>
- [8]. <https://palnetwork.org/what-do-we-mean-by-a-quality-education/>
- [9]. <https://www.drishitias.com/hindi/burning-issues-of-the-month/new-education-policy>
- [10]. Chinchkar, Shivaji <https://idronline.org/article/education/nep-2020-can-a-school-assessment-help-improve-our-quality-of-education/>
- [11]. Parikh, Rohan https://www.hindustantimes.com/education/how-nep-has-brought-a-paradigm-shift-from-quantity-to-quality-in-the-indian-education-system/story-XFBz9oBdpfN0Zl90I5UmbN_amp.html
- [12]. Kalyani, Pawan, (2020) ,” An Emperical Study of NEP 2020 (National Education Policy) with Special Reference to the Future of Indian Education System and Its effects on the Stakeholders “ Journal of Management Engineering and Information Technology (JMEIT),Volume 7 Issue 5, October 2020,Online ISSN :2394-8124.
- [13]. Kumar, K.(2005). Quality of Education at the Beginning of the 21st Century. Lesson from India. Indian Education Review.
- [14]. Venkateshwarlu, B.(2020). A Critical Study of NEP 2020 : ISSUES, Approaches , Challenges, Opportunities and Criticism. Internatrional Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research ,Volume 10.Issue 2(5),February.,2021,Online ISSN :2277-7881.